

FAIRsFAIR

Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe

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D5.1 FAIRsFAIR COMMUNICATION, MARKETING AND ENGAGEMENT PLAN

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Abstract

This document designs a coordinated set of actions for communicating FAIRSF AIR efficiently and to ensure coverage of stakeholders and adequate visibility of the project across Europe, sustaining the engagement figures and achieving the necessary concertation levels with INFRAEOSC-related initiatives.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HLAC	High Level Advisory Committee
EGFC	European Group of FAIR Champions
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DSM	Digital Single Market
EOSC EB	EOSC Executive Board
RDMF	Research Data Management Forum
IDCC	International Digital Curation Conference
ENVRI-FAIR	ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building Fair services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research
ESCAPE	European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures
PANOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
RDA	Research Data Alliance

Executive Summary

The overall objective of FAIRSF AIR is to accelerate the realization of the goals of the EOSC by opening up and sharing all knowledge, expertise, guidelines, implementations, new trajectories, courses and education on FAIR matters. It seeks to establish a level playing field for all European member states (and beyond) when it comes to contributing data to scientific and scholarly communities and to re-using data from scientists and scholars elsewhere. All this is made possible by the coordinated effort of twenty-two partners spanning eight member states that are working together to define guidelines towards a FAIR approach to data and service management for data repositories across disciplines.

In line with this goal, this document sets out a strategy for communication and dissemination, and provides **guidance to the project partners as to how to promote their activities to their respective target audiences and obtain maximum visibility.**

The document also contains an actionable communication plan with feasible KPIs and which describes all the European outreach activities that will be performed to support engagement with stakeholders.

The FAIRSF AIR communication strategy is a **SMART** (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound) and KPI-driven approach to successful community building and stakeholder engagement.

Section 1 of the plan presents the project **Communication and Outreach Strategy**, including the objectives and the communication campaigns that will support the engagement with each stakeholder group, and the monitoring mechanisms to assess their evolution. **Section 2** illustrates **FAIRSF AIR Governance in the context of the EOSC**, and the **FAIRSF AIR Stakeholders** are presented in **Section 3**. In **Section 4** those **FAIRSF AIR assets** which are the project “selling” points are listed, while **section 5** guides the reader through the **FAIRSF AIR Outreach & Communication plan**. The document closes with **section 6** offering insights on the **Communication and Engagement tools** to be used to make the plan as pragmatic as possible. Topics include branding, online presence and content production, print collateral and social media channel utilisation and distribution.

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1. Communication and Outreach Strategy

The “FAIRsFAIR Communication, Marketing and Engagement Plan (D5.1) is a 36-month strategy and addresses the following main aspects of FAIRsFAIR communication and outreach efforts:

- **the whom and why:** the target audiences for FAIRsFAIR messaging - which both promotes FAIR data principles and disseminates project outcomes in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC);
- **the what:** the communication activities that will evolve in line with the release of the key project assets and are designed to maximise visibility and ensure uptake of FAIRsFAIR results by scientific and scholarly communities, as well as by the other stakeholders identified.
- **the how and the how well:** how the communication activities will be implemented and how their effectiveness will be measured.

The plan defines a **continuous series of activities** also describes the creation of a large, international community with members from different European countries, sectors and disciplines, to maximise visibility and outreach. The aim is that these members, from scientific, industrial, political and other related sectors, will become FAIR multipliers, and, ultimately, active adopters of and advocates for FAIRsFAIR outcomes - a “FAIR data community” which understands the ideals and benefits of FAIR and their relation to innovation both as it applies to research and also in industry.

During the project, this **communication strategy will be updated and adapted in line with** progress in the implementation of Open and FAIR practices within the EOSC. There will also be close collaboration with the activities of the EOSC Working Group on FAIR and other EOSC FAIR-related initiatives.

1.1. Objectives and Value Proposition

The overall objective of FAIRsFAIR is to accelerate the realization of the goals of the EOSC by opening up and sharing all knowledge, expertise, guidelines, implementations, new approaches, courses and education on FAIR matters. It seeks to establish a level playing field for all European member states (and beyond) when it comes to contributing data to scientific and scholarly communities and to re-using data from scientists and scholars elsewhere.

To reach this objective, FAIRsFAIR has defined the present communication plan that is proportionate to the scale and scope of the project and based on the SMART approach: specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, targeted and timed. FAIRsFAIR will have a wide yet consistent communication approach and articulates around an online web platform (www.fairsfair.eu) integrated with social network channels, and offering high-quality resources and articles, branded promotional material and multimedia content designed to raise awareness, support training initiatives, and encourage FAIR adoption.

The key activities envisaged thus include:

- **Maintaining a coordinated and continued communication** of the FAIRsFAIR initiative, providing appropriate visibility to all stakeholders and supporting their engagement;
- Mapping the **FAIRsFAIR’s portfolio dissemination results** against each target stakeholder group;

- Installing a **European Group of Fair Champions (EGFC)**, representing the FAIRsFAIR stakeholders;
- Installing the **Synchronisation Task Force** that supports the EOSC governance structure, EOSC Board Working Groups and the EGFC;
- Organising **focused workshops**, aligned and possibly collocated with the EOSC main governance meetings, with a concertation focus on relevant initiatives that maximise project results;
- Developing an **effective strategy** to facilitate adoption for end users and obtain user feedback.

1.2. Monitoring the impact

WP5 is concerned with setting up a tailored Monitoring Service to track and measure the impact of the communication activities carried out. A shared dashboard will visually render all the relevant data from our communications and online activities. Necessary adjustments will be made during the course of the project. Alerts will be activated to keep partners informed of project activities.

The KPI tracker information tool is displayed in the figure below

	A	B
1	KPIs and Metrics for FAIRsFAIR Communication Strategy	
2	Toolbox element	Toolbox element
3	SEO-driven website and consultation platform	Measure the impact of the website in terms of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Min. 20 new content items/month; KPIs: 20,000 monthly sessions, 10,000 users, 80,000 page views. ● Campaigns to recruit contributions to the Consultation Platform with downloadable thematic reports. ● Qualitative metrics: profiling of website visits and visitors
4	Survey Campaigns (e.g. stakeholders, data standard practices etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Design and promotion of surveys for stakeholders on FAIR data practices, including competence centre priorities, and for other stakeholders. ● Min. 1 survey/quarter with graphically generated results (infographics) published on the consultation platform. ● Total: min. 12 surveys (mini and more detailed) with published results.
5	Press releases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Press releases/articles targeting the research user communities: Min 2/year. ● PRs/articles targeting stakeholders (policy and research funders): Min 1/year.
6	Collaterals and Promotional activities	Regularly updated flyers, brochures, posters etc. with impact analysing distribution and downloads, with tailored material for the outreach programme.
7	Videos & YouTube Channel	250 monthly views and 5 acquired subscriptions to the YouTube channel. Impact measures based on number of views
8	SlideShare	Uploading of slide decks on dedicated SlideShare account and promoted. Impact measures: number of views.
9	Social Media/Professional Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Measure community development and engagement. Min. 10 tweets/week + Twitter analytics ● Min. 5 posts/month on social media, monitored in terms of visibility, brand and reputation building.
10	Stakeholder engagement at events	Qualitative measures for participation in FAIRsFAIR and other events. Newcomers to FAIRsFAIR. Profiling of participants (gender, discipline, geographies, domain).
11	Clustering and Synergies	Measures qualitative & quantitative impact: new user communities, visibility, adoption & implementation stories, testimonials, etc.
12	Open Call Campaign	From month 1-5, an extensive Open Call SMART-based campaign with press release, media partners, social media banners and posts on social media, newsletters and promotion through events.
13	Outreach Campaigns	Extensive SMART-based campaigns specifically dedicated to the outreach programme to maximise participation and foster synergy-building. Specific targets will be defined depending on the event.
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2. FAIRSF AIR Governance in the context of the EOSC

The work of FAIRSF AIR supports the EOSC implementation by sustaining core data assets for the EOSC and making them available to the community under well-defined conditions. There is a strong focus on accelerating the certification of trusted repositories and the assessment of the FAIRness of data, software and services. FAIRSF AIR will be instrumental in making FAIR an indispensable concept to the community that deals with research data on a broad scale. Attunement to and co-operation with existing organisations, long-term projects and any other EOSC-supporting service providers and research infrastructures is at the heart of the project.

FAIRSF AIR's contribution to the EOSC is based on assuring that valuable research data and the benefits of data sharing are exploited to the maximum, in order to benefit society at large. For this, FAIR data principles must be spread all around Europe and the right skills imparted to all those that deal with data. It is thus the responsibility of the project to:

- **Collaborate closely with EOSC related projects and other initiatives;**
- **Organise and contribute to FAIR aspects of the EOSC framework;** in particular as regards harmonisation of policy and alignment of standards related to FAIR.
- **Contribute to the EOSC FAIR Working group,** set up by the European Commission;
- **Provide an open and inclusive consultation platform,** bringing specific benefits for all stakeholders and relevant outputs to support the EOSC ecosystem;
- **Contribute to the Rules of Participation in the EOSC¹,** for which another EOSC Working Group has been installed;
- Establish close cooperation with the EOSC Secretariat

In the table below are listed the upcoming FAIRSF AIR and other EOSC initiatives. Common work areas and synergies will be discussed with a view to arranging joint activities at these events. A list of EOSC related events is available in the following pages and FAIRSF AIR, along with EOSC Secretariat project, will discuss joint activities that can be put in place in these events.

Table 6 Next EOSC related events of relevance for FAIRSF AIR

Event	When	Target	Organised by	Envisaged collaboration	Main outcome
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¹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/rules-participation-working-group>

EOSC Workshop at Open Science Fair	16-18 September 2019 Porto (Portugal)	Researchers, Librarians and Policy Officers	EOSC Secretariat & OpenAIRE	III Edition of the "Services to support FAIR Data" Workshop 2 other workshops organized by FAIRSFAR FAIRSFAR GA	Post event report by the Synchronisation Force
EOSC event at RDA Finland	22 October 2019 Helsinki (Finland)	International Research Data Community	EOSC Secretariat	Participation to FAIR sessions	
EOSC Symposium	26-28 November 2019 Budapest (Hungary)	EOSC related projects & EOSC users	EOSC Secretariat	Synchronisation Force event & 1st meeting with the EGFC	First EOSC Synchronization White Paper
EOSC-hub week	18-20 May 2020 Karlsruhe (Germany)	EOSC Service providers	EOSC-hub	FAIRSFAR workshop	
EOSC Symposium	Fall 2020	EOSC related projects & EOSC users	EOSC Secretariat	Synchronisation Force event & 2nd meeting with the EGFC	Second EOSC Synchronization White Paper

In the following chapters, the FAIRSFAR governance structure and main collaboration with major EOSC players (e.g. EOSC Secretariat, EOSC 5B Projects, EOSC Working Groups, Cluster projects, amongst others) are described, as they represent the main drivers of the engagement with FAIRSFAR stakeholders.

2.1. FAIRSFAR and the EOSC WG on FAIR

The EOSC FAIR Working Group will provide recommendations on the implementation of Open and FAIR practices within the EOSC. It will address cross-disciplinary interoperability, gather requirements relevant to the EOSC services, and advise the EOSC Executive and Governance Boards on FAIR-related matters. The FAIR & Architecture WGs will operate in close alignment. The former addresses cultural aspects such as semantic and legal interoperability, certification, and community data standards, while the latter will focus on the related technical specifications that address FAIR requirements.

The implementation of FAIR and Open Science policy requires a culture change supported by appropriate incentives and coherent, easy-to-use data services. This WG will build on existing

FAIR practices in all disciplines and address interoperability across them. It will propose measures for increasing FAIR maturity to maximise data sharing and re-use.

The EOSC-FAIR Working Group will define and implement a FAIR work plan. This will be based on the Action Plan proposed by the EC Expert Group on “Turning FAIR into reality”, as well as ongoing community initiatives and outputs from key projects like FAIRsFAIR, RDA and FREYA.

The WG will provide recommendations on:

1. The development and adoption of data standards and sharing agreements
2. Best practices that are already applied in specific scientific domains or countries and can be adopted at the multi-disciplinary and European levels
3. An EOSC Interoperability Framework that overarches disciplinary approaches and encourages research infrastructures to be interoperable-by-design
4. Service requirements for FAIR implementation, relevant to the Architecture WG
5. A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the EOSC
6. Frameworks to assess FAIR data and certify services that enable FAIR, including the collation of results e.g. catalogues of certified repositories
7. The international dimension of FAIR principles, converging towards globally-accepted frameworks

2.2. FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force

The governance bodies of FAIRsFAIR – its General Assembly, Executive Committee and Project Coordination Office – will be assisted by a pan project Synchronisation Force for providing appropriate visibility to all stakeholders, by organising three focused workshops, for developing and tracking an effective uptake strategy to facilitate adoption of FAIR, while ensuring synchronisation with other initiatives, projects and EOSC governance.

The Synchronisation Force will be composed of representatives of the partners of the FAIRsFAIR project, nominated by the Work Package Leaders (maximum two per Work Package) in Month 3 of the project.

The members of the Synchronisation Force - supported by Task Leader 5.3 - are expected to participate in three workshops, contribute to the drafting of three reports in months 8, 17 and 23 of the project and to deliver a White paper in Month 26. The Synchronisation Force will liaise with the Expert Group of FAIR Champions (EGFC, Task 5.2) and the five ESFRI Clusters, PANOSC, SSHOC, ENVRIFAIR, ESCAPE, EOSC-Life, as well as the thematic and regional EOSC projects ('5b'). In the framework of the Collaboration Agreement between FAIRsFAIR and EOSC Secretariat, the Synchronisation Force will provide input for the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups on 'Landscape', 'FAIR', 'Sustainability', 'Architecture', 'Rules of Participation' at appropriate moments. Representatives of the EGFC, the ESFRI Clusters and the EOSC WGs will be invited as participants in the workshops.

Composition

FAIRsFAIR Synchronisation Force	member	member
WP 2	Jessica Parland-von Essen	Josefine Nordling
WP 3	Joy Davidson	Angus Whyte
WP 4	Ilona von Stein	Hervé L'Hours
WP 5	Sara Pittonet	Vanessa Proudman
WP 6	Brian Matthews	Hugh Shanahan
WP 7	Lennart Stoy	Bregt Saenen

2.3. HLAC – the High Level Advisory Committee

The High Level Advisory Committee (HLAC) will be appointed by the EXC and is composed of six to nine international experts and a chair with a proven track record either from research, industrial, funders, standardisation and/or publishing point of view. The role of the HLAC members is to advise on the project's strategy. The gain for the project is to add independent opinions to the way the project proceeds. The engagement will involve 6-monthly calls and 2 to 3 physical meetings for the duration of the project, organised by the Project Coordination Office in consultation with the Executive Board.

A dedicated page is available on FAIRsFAIR website:

<https://www.fairsfair.eu/advisory-board/hlac>

2.4. EGFC – The European Group of FAIR Champions

The European Group of FAIR Champions (EGFC) will be composed of 15 scientific experts and “doers” in the field of FAIR data, carefully selected based on their individual merits and knowledge. The group works as an ambassador of FAIR by sharing FAIR implementation stories, enhancing synergies, contributing to training activities (e.g. workshops) and webinars, and doing an effective cross-fertilization with other communities, towards a broader engagement on FAIR.

Main tasks. Champions are expected to contribute to the **Pan-European Uptake Interim and Final Report** (D5.2 and D5.7) that will feed and fuel the EOSC Executive Board (EB) Working Group on FAIR. They will act as ambassadors within their communities to create broader

engagement with FAIR and shape and disseminate the outcomes of the project. They will also be actively engaged during the **Landscape Analysis** activity and asked to fill in the surveys set-up by WP3.

The content produced by the EGFC through the outreach channels (i.e. webinars, workshops) will support the White Paper report(s) (*M5.4 EOSC Synchronization White Paper(s)*) to be produced by the “Synchronization Task Force” that will feed into the EOSC EB WG on FAIR.

The members of the EGFC agree to:

- Actively engage with your community on FAIRsFAIR developments and advocate for results to be adopted and applied in your community using a range of methods/media
- Meet **bi-monthly**, through conference calls, promoting a holistic vision of FAIR, strongly encouraging multi-view discussions and addressing the ethical and regulatory aspects at hand with the technological aspects and the end users’ perception;
- Meet **face-to-face** during the project timeframe in conjunction with the FAIRsFAIR Synchronization Task Force Workshops
- Provide success stories which may be published on the website;
- Participate in **webinars as invited speakers** and contribute valuable content to any physical meetings/workshops/events organised;
- Maintain confidentiality on all technical and business information and material exchanged. The confidential information may refer to technical developments, research and innovation, business and financial data, customer information, costs and profit data and other information belonging to any of the parties involved that is not intended for public dissemination;
- **Evaluate your user experience** by answering a short questionnaire & providing your comments.

Five (5) members have already been nominated by the FAIRsFAIR Executive Committee in May 2019 (M3) after a selection procedure aiming to achieve a well-balanced representation of views, priorities, needs, disciplines and gender. Nine (9) additional members will be selected by the FAIRsFAIR Executive Committee via an Open Call to be launched in July 2019 and open until M18.

At the time of writing of this report, five invited experts accepted the invitation and the Terms of Reference (ToR) prepared by FAIRsFAIR are now being signed.

Table 4 First six members of EGFC

Name	Institution	Skill set relevant for FAIRsFAIR
Alastair Dunning The Netherlands, Male	TU Delft	Alastair is Head of Research Data Services at TU Delft & Head of 4TU.Centre for Research Data
Odile Hologne, France, Female	INRA	Odile is head of the department of scientific information of Inra, the French research institute in agriculture,

		environment and food. She's been involved in many different projects from data sharing policy to repositories development. She is a member of the science europe working group on open access to research data
Andreas Rauber, Austria, Male	Tech Uni Vienna & RDA Europe	Strong research data advocate, good communicator, ambitious, team-player, Andreas Rauber is Associate Professor at the Department of Software Technology and Interactive Systems (ifs) at the Vienna University of Technology (TU-Wien). He furthermore is president of AARIT, the Austrian Association for Research in IT, a Key Researcher at Secure Business Austria (SBA-Research) and Co-Chair and member of several RDA Working and Interest Groups. His research interests cover the broad scope of digital libraries and information spaces, including specifically text and music information retrieval and organization, information visualization, as well as data analysis and digital preservation, all of which start to merge recently under the umbrella of reproducible science.
Susanna-Assunta Sansone UK, Female	Oxford e-Research Centre, FAIRsharing	Susanna is Associate Director, Associate Professor and Principal Investigator at the Oxford e-Research Centre. She is a Consultant for Springer Nature, and Founding Honorary Academic Editor of the Scientific Data journal. She is co-author of the FAIR principles and of the FAIRmetric. She is a founding and/or on the Board of several international grass-roots standards, advocacy groups and non-for-profit efforts, including the Research Data Alliance.
Tobias Weigel, Germany, Male	DKRZ	Tobias works for the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) with a focus on the development of e-science infrastructure components and operational concepts for PIDs. He is a Member of the RDA Technical Advisory Board and co-chair of groups on Research Data Collections, Data Fabric and Data Type Registries.

A dedicated logo was created to identify EGFC to third parties, along with a dedicated page on FAIRSFair website <https://www.fairsfair.eu/advisory-board/egfc>, introducing the EGFC mission and its members.

2.5. FAIRSFair Collaboration with EOSC Secretariat

EOSC Secretariat delivers 360° support to the EOSC Governance while working openly and inclusively with communities to co-create an all-encompassing European Open Science Cloud. FAIRSFair is engaging with EOSC Secretariat to jointly collect information about FAIR practices and implementation at regional and national levels. This will directly feed in FAIRSFair landscape analysis and support the engagement with the EOSC 5B projects.

A collaboration agreement was signed in June 2019 (M4) between FAIRSFAR & EOSC Secretariat, to synchronise and coordinate activities divided in the following focus areas:

- **Identification of overlaps and complementarities** between FAIRSFAR, EOSCSecretariat.eu in order to jointly support the implementation of the EOSC and development of a synchronised plan of activities.
- Development of a common **strategy to synchronise activities of FAIRSFAR with the EOSC Working Groups;**
- Synchronise stakeholder mapping, stakeholder engagement and cross-fertilisation of expertise and people;
- **Develop a common strategy** to liaise with the regional and thematic EOSC projects ('INFRAEOSC-5b-2018-2019'), in order to create optimal synergies.
- Collaborate on outreach and dissemination

The table below provides more detailed information about the joint activities between FAIRSFAR and EOSC Secretariat. This work plan will be updated as appropriate.

Table 7 FAIRSFAR & EOSC Secretariat Joint Activity Plan

Synergy Area	Activities	Milestone
Identification of overlaps and complementarities between FAIRSFAR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Organise 2 Concertation/Synchronization Working meetings per year dedicated to presentation and exchange of information about the planned activities of each of the two projects; · Develop an online shared coordinated plan of activities updated every six months. Specific sections of this plan will be formulated as part of the activities that are described in the rest of this Agreement. 	First version of the Coordinated Plans of Activities in Month 5 (updated every six months).
Development of a common strategy to synchronise activities of FAIRSFAR with the EOSC Working Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·EOSCSecretariat.eu will keep FAIRSFAR continuously updated about WGs plans and activities; ·EOSCSecretariat.eu will inform FAIRSFAR about needs and outcomes that will emerge from the EOSC WGs that are relevant to FAIRSFAR activities; ·FAIRSFAR will provide input and feedback produced by its experts to the EOSC WGs; ·Members of the FAIRSFAR Synchronisation Force will actively participate in EOSC Liaisons Groups set up by EOSCSecretariat.eu. 	First input for WG meetings (three months after the installation of the WGs).

<p>Synchronise stakeholder mapping, stakeholder engagement and cross fertilisation of expertise and people</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·Develop a common strategy to coordinate activities such as surveys, landscape analyses and working meetings; ·Roll out targeted activities to involve researchers, industry and infrastructure providers in co-design and co-creation of EOSC, regarding FAIR data management; · Prepare for leverage with international implementation networks; ·Identify and exploit synergies in building and populating the FAIRsFAIR and the EOSCSecretariat.eu Stakeholder communities; ·Co-organise 1 FAIR coordination meeting per year involving different FAIR-related initiatives. The outputs of the meeting will be delivered to the FAIR WG; · Promote the FAIRsFAIR results at the EOSC FAIR-related events organised by the EOSCSecretariat.eu and vice versa; ·Organise 2 joint webinars on FAIR data management. 	<p>First FAIR-related event; Second FAIR-related event.</p>
<p>Develop a common strategy to liaise with the regional and thematic EOSC projects in order to create optimal synergies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ·Develop a plan aimed at reducing duplications and optimising liaising activities with INFRAEOSC-5b-2018-2019 will be prepared and continuously updated; ·Organise Periodic meetings to discuss progress with respect to the plan indicated above. 	<p>Initial release of the on-line plan for liaising with 'INFRAEOSC-5b-2018-2019' projects (M6).</p>
<p>Collaborate on outreach and dissemination</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Joint dissemination and coordination events; ·Disseminate each other's outcomes, e.g. FAIRsFAIR outcomes disseminated by EOSCSecretariat.eu to its stakeholders' network (e.g. researchers, private companies, national and international infrastructures) and EOSCSecretariat.eu activities and co-creation opportunities disseminated to FAIRsFAIR addressed stakeholder. 	<p>First joint event in Month 9.</p>

This agreement involves not only the EOSC 5B projects and EOSC ESFRI Clusters but also the FREYA, EOSChub, e-InfraCentral, OpenAIRE, RDA Europe and the OCRE and ARCHIVER, who will be observers.

2.6. Cluster Projects

The five cluster projects (funded under the "INFRAEOSC-04-2018" call), ensure the connection of research infrastructures to the EOSC, from different thematic domains, while addressing

the stewardship of data handled according to the FAIR principles. Each one will produce a significant amount of data, along with novel services which, ultimately, will be exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services. FAIRSF AIR is engaging with these projects to support them with practical guidance on making their data FAIR compliant.

For each of them, a contact person has already been identified to act as a liaison between FAIRSF AIR and the cluster project and support in the mutual dissemination and promotion

Table 5 The five EOSC Cluster projects

Project	Topic	Goal
ENVRI-FAIR	Environment	Implement the ENVRI-hub - a virtual, federated machine-to-machine interface to access environmental data and services provided by the contributing RIs. The complete set of thematic data services and tools will be incorporated into the EOSC service catalogue, through the EOSC-hub Marketplace
EOSC-Life	Biological & Medical	Bring together biological and medical RIs to create an open collaborative space for digital biology. It aims to publish FAIR life science data resources for cloud use creating an ecosystem of innovative tools in EOSC and enabling groundbreaking data-driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC
ESCAPE	Astronomy & Particle Physics	Bring together ESFRI facilities of astronomy, astroparticle & particle physics into a single EU collaborative cluster. Plus, it will create a cross-border & multi-disciplinary environment that will benefit EOSC thanks to the management of extremely large data volumes at the multi-exabyte level. It will also support “scientific software” as a major component of RI data to be preserved and exposed in EOSC through dedicated catalogues
PANOSC	Photon and Neutron Sciences	Help the Photon and Neutron ESFRIs to adopt and implement data management, simulation and analysis services, and to make their open data available to the EOSC. It will work closely with EOSC-hub partners to integrate general-purpose distributed computing and data management solutions and promote its products through the EOSC Portal.
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities	Provide an open cloud for social sciences and humanities where data, tools, and training are available and accessible for users. This open cloud aims to be a part of the EOSC. The consortium covers the whole data cycle, from data creation and curation, to optimal data reuse, and can

		address training and advocacy to increase actual reuse of data.
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Target communication activities include:

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
Participation to FAIRsFAIR & EOSC events	The Cluster projects will be invited to join the FAIRsFAIR workshop at the Open Science Forum in Porto and the Synchronisation Force event during the EOSC Symposium	Inputs from the Cluster projects included in the first EOSC Synchronization White Paper
FAIRsFAIR news pieces on websites	FAIRsFAIR news pieces shared on the clusters websites	Reaching out to the clusters specific communities; backlinks and referrals for FAIRsFAIR website
Press releases distribution	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR press releases via the clusters network	Reaching out to the clusters specific communities
Content production & Open Calls promotion	Creation of a template for Best practice on FAIR, invitation to be part of the EGFC, invitation to join TF workshops & webinars, distribute white paper & invitation to subscribe to FAIRsFAIR newsletter	Informing and engaging the related thematic community about FAIRsFAIR outcomes
Social media sharing	Continuous content sharing with personal and company accounts	Retweets, Likes and followers in each FAIRsFAIR social media channels from clusters and clusters community members

2.7. EOSC 5b Projects

The recently funded projects under the “Coordination of EOSC-relevant national initiatives across Europe and support to prospective EOSC service providers” call (‘INFRAEOSC-5b-2018-2019’), known as EOSC 5B projects, are national initiatives across Europe that are supporting the EOSC implementation in different EU countries. These 5 projects are fostering coordination, convergence and federation of EOSC relevant national initiatives for open research data and services, through the development of appropriate common tools and mechanisms.

All in all, the projects' main goal is to contribute to the mapping and harmonisation of the procedures regulating the delivery of horizontal services related to research data by prospective EOSC service providers and by national initiatives located in different Member States and Associated Countries. This is done not only by gradually align policies and practices of EOSC national initiatives to the EOSC standards, but also enabling EOSC relevant non-commercial services to be accessed through EOSC portal.

Within the framework of the Collaboration agreement with EOSC Secretariat, FAIRsFAIR will develop a **common strategy to liaise with the regional and thematic EOSC projects**, in order to create optimal synergies.

Table 8 EOSC 5B Projects

Project	Region Covered	Goals
ExPaNDS	10 European countries with Photon & Neutron research infrastructures and federated e-infrastructures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enable EOSC services and provide coherent FAIR data services to the scientific users of PaN sources · Connect PaN NRIs through a platform of data analysis as a service for users from research institutes universities, industry etc. · Maintain and develop a catalogue of data and analysis software for PaN data · Gather feedback and cooperate with the EOSC governance bodies to improve the EOSC · Develop standard relationships between scientific publications, PaN scientific datasets, experimental reports, instruments, authors
EOSC-Nordic	Nordic and Baltic area: Denmark, Finland, Estonia, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway and Sweden	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Support coordination, harmonisation and alignment of Nordic and Baltic national policies and practices related to the provision of horizontal research data services with EOSC · Increase the discoverability of Nordic & Baltic services. Extend and expand their use by making them accessible through the EOSC portal · Promote and support the uptake of FAIR data practices and certification schemas across the Nordics · Accelerate the progress and attractiveness of EOSC by piloting & delivering innovative solutions developed and tested in a useful and functional cross-border environment · Provide a Knowledge Hub to deliver training and technical support to new service providers and communities willing to engage with EOSC during and after the project lifetime

EOSC-Pillar	Western Europe: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Analyse the state of the art of existing national initiatives and services for computing and data services in the countries involved, and support their consolidation · Harmonise procedures for the delivery of horizontal enabling services for research data across countries · Co-ordinate with other initiatives to achieve harmonisation across different regions, countries, and trans-national research communities to build a truly inclusive EOSC · Promote the uptake of FAIR data practices and services at national levels and across scientific communities and national borders · Enable non-commercial trans-national services to be accessed through the EOSC portal · Support the growth of an active community of stakeholders in each involved country, who will actively contribute to the success of EOSC · Propose viable business models for the sustainable provision of trans-national services
EOSC-Synergy	Iberic Peninsula & other EU countries: Czech Republic, Germany, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain and The Netherlands.	Expand the Capacity and Capabilities of EOSC by leveraging the experience, effort and resources of national publicly funded digital infrastructures in a coherent way, therefore acting also as an incentive for national resource providers.
NI4OS-Europe	South-Eastern Europe: Albania, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Cyprus, Greece, Hungary, Macedonia, Moldavia, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia and Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Support EOSC governance framework by building national Open Science Cloud (OSC) initiatives for open research data, infrastructure and services and enabling them to support the overall EOSC governance and the related EOSC coordination structure. · Facilitate the federation of existing infrastructures and state-of-the-art services and their on-boarding to EOSC. · Enable the EOSC-relevant, non-commercial services to be accessed through the EOSC portal. · Technical, organizational and legal guidelines, tools, mechanisms and certification schemes, to support Open Research Data Management and its implementation in a harmonised and coordinated fashion. · Ensure the engagement of the targeted communities and validate the project solutions.

A first meeting with all EOSC 5B projects, between 6-7 June 2019, was facilitated by EOSC Secretariat, which allowed to align communication channels between these projects and other EOSC initiatives.

Target communication initiatives include:

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
Participation to FAIRsFAIR & EOSC events	The 5b projects will be invited to join the FAIRsFAIR workshop at the Open Science Forum in Porto and the Synchronisation Force event during the EOSC Symposium	Inputs from the 5b projects included in the first EOSC Synchronization White Paper
FAIRsFAIR news pieces on websites	FAIRsFAIR news pieces shared on the EOSC5b project websites	Reaching out to the clusters specific communities; backlinks and referrals for FAIRsFAIR website
Press releases distribution	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR press releases via the EOSC5b network	Reaching out to the EOSC5b specific communities
Joint dissemination and coordination events	Invitation to join TF workshops & webinars, distribute white papers & invitation to subscribe to FAIRsFAIR newsletter	Informing and engaging the related national community about FAIRsFAIR outcomes
Joint dissemination at National / regional level	FAIRsFAIR outcomes disseminated EOSC 5b national/regional stakeholders e.g. researchers, private companies, national and international infrastructures)	Outreach of national actors not already part in the FAIRsFAIR & EOSC Secretariat teams
Social media sharing	Continuous content sharing with personal and company accounts	Retweets, Likes and followers in each FAIRsFAIR social media channels from clusters and clusters community members
Online plan & periodic report	Online plan and periodic reporting of the joint activities	Results and activities of the Joint Activity Plan periodically reported upon, and described in the two projects Periodic Progress Activity Reports

2.8. Other FAIR Initiatives

The FAIRSF AIR consortium partners are active in a number of relevant European Open Science initiatives including the **Research Data Alliance (RDA)** and RDA Europe, **OpenAIRE**, the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) pilot project and Executive Board**, and the training Implementation Network of the **GO-FAIR initiative**. In addition, FAIRSF AIR has links to the **European Commission's High Level Expert Group on 'Turning FAIR data into reality via Sarah Jones from DCC**. Our connections with these related initiatives will be invaluable as we seek to align efforts and avoid duplication of effort.

2.9. FAIRSF AIR Partners as facilitators

All FAIRSF AIR partners will have an important role in communicating project results to and through their networks. Below are listed the specific activities to be performed by partners in WP 5. The list is not exhaustive.

Digital Curation Centre (DCC), UK

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk>

Established in 2004, the Digital Curation Centre is a collaborative organisation that seeks primarily to empower and enable others to do more with FAIR research data. DCC provides access to a range of tools, resources, and training as well as providing expert advice to organisations on data management and increasing impact through the adoption of open research and FAIR data practices. The DCC has fostered a global network of stakeholders and is an active participant in a number of relevant European Open Science initiatives including the **Research Data Alliance (RDA) and RDA Europe, OpenAIRE, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) pilot project and Executive Board**, and the training Implementation Network of the **GO-FAIR initiative**. We will also make use of our successful social media channels, annual International Digital Curation Conference, and bi-annual Research Data Management Forums (RDMF) to help promote the activities of FAIRSF AIR to encourage community feedback to help shape the outcomes our work to maximise their value to communities of practice. In particular, DCC will leverage our connections with European HEIs, funding bodies, and research infrastructures to help map the current policy, practice and competency landscape with regards to making data FAIR and to collaboratively develop recommendations to increase FAIR data production and use.

Main stakeholders: EOSC WG on FAIR, RDA FAIR Data Maturity WG, GO-FAIR

Target communication activities include:

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
FAIRSF AIR page on main website	1 page published on DCC website describing FAIRSF AIR and DCC's role	Visibility & recognition towards DCC's stakeholders; backlink & referral to the FAIRSF AIR website

Press releases distribution	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR press releases via DCC mailing lists and newsletters	Reaching out 1.000 of users not part of FAIRsFAIR database
Presentation & visibility at key EOSC events	Visibility for FAIRsFAIR at the IDCC and RDMF events	Promotion of FAIRsFAIR assets and calls to action
Promotion of FAIRsFAIR Open Calls	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR open calls announcements via DCC mailing lists and newsletters	Reaching out 1.000 of users not part of FAIRsFAIR database
Updates towards EOSC WG on FAIR	Updates about FAIRsFAIR during the meetings of the EOSC EB & WG on FAIR	Direct discussion channel with the EOSC
Social media sharing	Continuous production of posts and content sharing with personal and company accounts	Retweets, Likes and followers in each FAIRsFAIR social media channels from DCC community members

European University Association (EUA), Belgium

www.eua.eu

The European University Association (EUA) represents more than 800 universities and national rectors' conferences in 48 European countries. EUA plays a crucial role in the Bologna Process and in influencing European policies on higher education, research and innovation. Through continuous interaction with a range of other European and international organisations, EUA ensures that the independent voice of **European universities** is heard. A wide range of activities and events make the Association the foremost university forum for exchange of ideas and good practice in higher education, research and innovation. EUA is an active member of the EOSC community and a signatory of the 2017 EOSC Declaration. Results of activities and events are communicated to our members via a newsletter (+/- 12,000 recipients), website, social media channels, targeted mailings and expert groups, all of which will feature regular updates on the FAIRsFAIR project. In addition, EUA provides unrivalled opportunities for members to share best practices by participating in projects such as FAIRsFAIR, events and other mutual-learning activities involving a wide range of universities.

Main stakeholders: European Universities and University Associations

Target communication activities include:

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
FAIRsFAIR page on main website	1 page published on DCC website describing FAIRsFAIR and EUA's role	Visibility & recognition towards DCC's stakeholders; backlink & referral to the FAIRsFAIR website

Press releases distribution	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR press releases via EUA targeted mailings and expert groups and newsletters	Reaching out 12.000 of users not part of FAIRsFAIR database
Dissemination of findings and assets	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR landscape analyses results, Surveys, Focus Groups updates, and capacity building workshops from WP7 and WP3 (policies)	Reaching out 12.000 of users not part of FAIRsFAIR database
Social media sharing	Continuous production of posts and content sharing with personal and company accounts	Retweets, Likes and followers in each FAIRsFAIR social media channels from EUA community members

Data Archiving and Networked Services - DANS, the Netherlands

<https://dans.knaw.nl/>

DANS (Data Archiving and Networked Services) is the Netherlands Institute for permanent access to digital research resources. DANS encourages researchers to make their digital research data and related outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. DANS provides [expert advice](#) and [certified services](#). The institutes has three core services: [DataverseNL](#) for short-term data management, [EASY](#) for long-term archiving, and [NARCIS](#), the national portal for research information. By participating in a broad range of projects among which OpenAIRE, SSHOC, EOSC-hub and FREAY, DANS is an important player in the European and global network of scientific data infrastructure. DANS is an institute of the Dutch Academy [KNAW](#) and funding organisation [NWO](#).

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
FAIRsFAIR page on DANS website	1 section published on the DANS website describing DANS' role and involvement in FAIRsFAIR	Visibility & recognition towards DANS' stakeholders; reference to the FAIRsFAIR website
News items on main page	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR publications, news items and success stories	Making FAIRsFAIR's work known among DANS's stakeholders
News items in newsletter (e-data & research)	Publication of news items about FAIRsFAIR's work in one of the best-read newsletters on research data in the Netherlands	Expanding the outreach of the work done in FAIRsFAIR beyond DANS' own website

Social media	Use of social media channels such as Twitter to improve the visibility of FAIRSF AIR	Retweets, likes and followers for FAIRSF AIR’s social media channels, broaden and expand the community
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IT Center for Science - CSC, Finland

www.csc.fi

CSC – IT Center for Science is a Finnish center of expertise in information technology owned by the Finnish state and higher education institutions. CSC provide internationally high-quality ICT expert services for higher education institutions, research institutes, culture, public administration and enterprises to help them thrive and benefit society at large.

CSC is a non-profit state enterprise with special tasks. As part of the national research system, we develop, integrate and provide high-quality information technology services and ensure that Finland remains at the forefront of development. Nice to know: one of the most powerful supercomputers in the world is invested in Finland and it will be [placed in the CSC Datacenter in Kajaani](#).

CSC has an important role as an instrument for steering and developing the Ministry of Education and Culture's education, science and cultural policy. Our primary customers are the Ministry of [Education](#) and Culture and organizations in the field, higher education institutions (universities and universities of applied sciences), [research institutes](#) and [public administration](#).

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
Reaching out Finnish Policy and decision Makers	FAIRSF AIR White paper and other relevant deliverables shared with the Ministry of Education and Culture's education, science and cultural policy	FAIRSF AIR recommendation received and addressed by the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture's education, science and cultural policy in any national roadmap documents for data repositories
FAIRSF AIR news on CSC’s websites	FAIRSF AIR news pieces shared on the CSC’s websites	Making FAIRSF AIR’s work known among CSC’s stakeholders
Press releases	Distribution of FAIRSF AIR press releases via the CSC network to Finnish Policy and decision Makers	Reaching out to the CSC specific communities
Social media	Continuous content sharing with personal and company accounts	Retweets, Likes and followers in each FAIRSF AIR social media channels from clusters and clusters community members

Newsletters	Publication of news items about FAIRsFAIR in our several newsletters	Expanding the outreach of the work done in FAIRsFAIR beyond CSC's own website
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The Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)

<http://stfc.ukri.org>

STFC is one of the Research Councils within UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) (www.ukri.org) which brings UK research funding into one organisation. STFC supports research in astronomy, particle physics, nuclear physics, and space science, as well as the UK's contribution to international science at for example CERN and ESO.

STFC funds and operates large-scale scientific facilities across the physical and life sciences. in the UK (e.g. ISIS Neutron and Muon Source, Diamond Light Source, Central Laser Facility (CLF)) and is responsible for UK access to European facilities (e.g. ESRF, ILL, ESS, EU-XFEL). STFC's Scientific Computing Department (SCD) provides large-scale computing resources and expertise in scientific computing to the STFC science programme and its partners within UK and worldwide.

SCD has been at the forefront of efforts to promote Open Science. It has been instrumental in open data policy at UK Research Council, European and G7 level. It has been an organisational member of the Research Data Alliance, participating in the sequence of RDA Europe projects. It has led the European Open Science Cloud-Pilot project, leads the FREYA project on the use of Persistent Identifiers, participates in the EOSC Executive, and is a partner in the EOSC projects, EOSC-Hub, EOSC-Secretariat, and EXPANDS.

STFC will make use of its central role in the UK's research community to promote the FAIRsFAIR project aims in coordinating and developing FAIR policy, practises and competencies. In particular, it will reach out to its core communities in Physics, Astronomy, and facilities science, which has a wide reach across chemical, materials and life sciences.

Target communication activities include:

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
FAIRsFAIR page on main website	1 page published on STFC-SCD website describing FAIRsFAIR and STFC's role	Visibility & recognition towards STFC's stakeholders; backlink & referral to the FAIRsFAIR website
Press releases distribution	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR press releases via STFC-SCD Social Media	Reaching out 1000 users not part of FAIRsFAIR database
Presentation & visibility at key EOSC events	Visibility for FAIRsFAIR at the range of open science and science domain events	Promotion of FAIRsFAIR assets and calls to action

Promotion of FAIRSF AIR Open Calls	Distribution of FAIRSF AIR open calls announcements via STFC-SCD Social Media	Reaching over 1000 users not part of FAIRSF AIR database
Updates towards EOSC WG on Rules of Participation	Updates about FAIRSF AIR during the meetings of the EOSC EB & WG on Rules of Participation	Direct discussion channel with the EOSC
Social media sharing	Use of social media channels such as STFC-SCD Twitter account to improve the visibility of FAIRSF AIR	Retweets, Likes and followers in each FAIRSF AIR social media channels from STFC community members

University of Bremen (UniHB), Germany

<https://www.pangaea.de/>

The University of Bremen is a public university in Germany and hosts the excellence cluster MARUM (Center for Marine Environmental Sciences). Jointly with the Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research at the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), MARUM hosts PANGAEA, an information system and publisher for earth and environmental data. PANGAEA is, or was involved in, a variety of EU projects focusing on research infrastructures and associated data management such as THOR, FREYA, ESONET, FixO3, COOPEUS and COOP+, EMSO, HYPOX, SIOS and Common Operations of Environmental Research infrastructures (ENVRI and ENVRIplus). Further, PANGAEA serves as long-term data archive for data which was collected during many European projects, such as the Atlantic Data Base for Exchange Processes at the Deep Sea Floor (ADEPD), Assessment of the Black Sea Sedimentary System since the last Glacial Extreme (ASSEMBLAGE), Biogas Transfer in Estuaries (BIOGEST), CARBOOCEAN, CoralFISH, DARCLIFE, EUR-OCEANS, EURO-BASIN, EPOCA, ERA-CLIM, ESONET, ESOP, HERMES, HERMIONE, HYPOC, MATER, METROL, ORFOIS, PROMESS, SINOPS, etc.

Main stakeholders: Research institutions, Researchers

Target communication activities include:

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
FAIRSF AIR page on PANGAEA website	1 section published on PANGAEA website describing FAIRSF AIR and UniHB's role in the project.	Visibility & recognition towards UniHB's stakeholders; backlink & referral to the FAIRSF AIR website

Dissemination of findings and assets	Publication of 2 abstracts on the data assessment requirements and tool that will be developed as part of FAIRSF AIR at scientific events.	Expanding the outreach of the work done in FAIRSF AIR beyond PANGAEA.
Social media sharing	Continuous production of posts and content sharing with personal and company accounts	Retweets, Likes and followers in each FAIRSF AIR social media channels from PANGAEA community members

SPARC (the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition)

SPARC (the Scholarly Publishing and Academic Resources Coalition) Europe is a non-profit, member organisation comprised of a diverse body of academic institutions, library consortia, research institutes and some publishers, among others. We are committed to making Open the default in Europe's research and education communities mainly supporting research performing organisations (RPOs).

Since SPARC Europe's founding in 2004, it has been a key player in driving Open Access forward by influencing open policies in Europe and working with European institutions such as the European Commission, Europe's research institutions and universities, and organisations with allied Open agendas. SPARC Europe consistently initiates, facilitates and supports the implementation of the long-term objective of opening access to European research for all. Our work centres around 3 goals: Driving Open Access, expanding access to research data and Accelerating Open Education in Europe through policy development and advocacy programmes.

SPARC Europe's data efforts centre around arming policy-makers with the information they need, providing much-needed guidance on multiple fronts – and addressing the cultural issues that create barriers:

- Conducting research in the European Open Science policy arena to inform Europe's Open Science policy makers of policy developments in Open Data and Open Science concerning research data in Europe.
- Conducting policy-making on a European level, influencing the development of the PSI directive for example
- Producing Open Data case studies for re-use by both research data advocates and Open Science / Scholarship policy-makers.
- Providing guidance to research performing organisations, their libraries, data supporters and senior management through briefings on topics such as evidence in the open data citation advantage how to use open data policy to increase research efficiency or the role of Open data in research integrity
- Helping to stimulate cultural change in research institutions through SPARC Europe's champions programme, and through a new showcase Europe's Open data Champions based on Europe's Open Access champions. For more information, see experience below.

- We are well connected in Europe; i.e. with DCC, LIBER, EBLIDA, IFLA, Science Europe, EUA, and other strong network organisations that serve academic library communities, their research communities as well as funders.

Main stakeholders: academic libraries and other organisations, publishers and policy makers

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
Reaching out to SPARC Europe members	Sharing key FAIRSF AIR deliverables, in particular policy ones, including also the FAIRSF AIR White Paper	Awareness raising of FAIRSF AIR recommendations and information on good practise amongst academic libraries and other organisations across over 25 countries (SPARC Europe members) and beyond
FAIRSF AIR blog posts on SPARC Europe website	FAIRSF AIR news items / blog posts published on the SPARC Europe website	Awareness of FAIRSF AIR progress amongst SPARC Europe members and the broader scholarly communications community
Press releases	Distribution of FAIRSF AIR press releases via the CSC network to Finnish Policy and decision Makers	Reaching out to the CSC specific communities
Social media	Sharing key news via SPARC_EU twitter account and response to FAIRSF AIR social media postings	SPARC Europe a follower of FAIRSF AIR social media channels and retweets, visibly an advocate and supporter of FAIRSF AIR on social media, also by actively sharing news via SPARC_EU
SPARC Europe newsletter	Publication of news items on FAIRSF AIR in SPARC Europe newsletter	Awareness on FAIRSF AIR raised in the scholarly communications community

Trust-IT, Italy

<https://trust-itservices.com>

Trust-IT has been at the centre of the work towards realising the **European Open Science Cloud**, from laying the science cloud’s foundations in [EOSCpilot](#), to ensuring the first set of services in [EOSC-hub](#), to the development of the [EOSC Portal](#) central access point, and through Trust-IT’s CEO Silvana Muscella’s chairmanship of the [European Commission’s EOSC High Level Expert Group](#) during the critical period of the EOSC launch.

Post-EOSC launch, the company continues to work towards strengthening the EOSC such as reducing the barrier for private sector cloud service providers in [OCRE](#), ensuring the buy in of the thematic research infrastructures in ESCAPE and SSHOC, ensuring the inclusion of national and domain-specific initiatives in [EOSC-Pillar](#) and supports the EOSC Executive Governing Boards through the [EOSC Secretariat.eu](#).

Moreover, Trust-IT works with e-infrastructure providers and data practitioners worldwide to support the provision of national, pan-European and global e-infrastructures. Trust-IT's expertise in this field is relevant in today's activities with EUDAT CDI, to which Trust-IT is a member, and the [Research Data Alliance](#) Europe, which it currently coordinates, as well as the RDA Secretariat that counts two members from Trust-IT.

Activity	Description	Envisaged impact
FAIRsFAIR page on Trust-IT website	1 section published on the Trust-IT website describing Trust-IT's role and involvement in FAIRsFAIR	Visibility & recognition towards Trust-IT's stakeholders; reference to the FAIRsFAIR website
News items on main page	Distribution of FAIRsFAIR publications, news items and success stories	Making FAIRsFAIR's work known among Trust-IT's stakeholders
News items in EOSC related project websites and newsletters	Publication of news items on relevant EOSC related projects, namely EOSC Secretariat, EOSC Pillar, ESCAPE, OCRE and ARCHIVER, RDA, when relevant	Expanding the outreach of the work done in FAIRsFAIR via the EOSC and RDA channels
Social media	Use of social media channels such as Twitter to improve the visibility of FAIRsFAIR	Retweets, likes and followers for FAIRsFAIR's social media channels, broaden and expand the community

3. FAIRsFAIR Stakeholders

Target audiences' definition and segmentation are crucial to ensure effective impact and select the most appropriate messaging tools and communication channels, for seeking and consolidating synergies with all relevant initiatives, community gatekeepers and multipliers. The FAIRsFAIR target audiences have different value propositions, engagement priorities, and distinct communication activities.

Figure 1 FAIRSFAR Stakeholders

3.1. End-users & other direct beneficiaries (primary audience)

Researchers, Large Enterprises, Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and Citizen scientists. The main engagement activities are based on the launch of targeted messaging, organisation of tailored events and training, as well as online engagement through social media presence.

Stakeholder	Description	Sample
Researchers	Practitioners, from all fields of humanities and science, creating new knowledge, products, processes, methods and systems, whose data should be properly managed and published to enable reproducible research.	European Educational Research Association; European Urban Research Association; European Science Education Research Association; European Council for Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers; European Educational Research Association and individual researchers working for academia & industry.
Large Enterprises	Industry organisations from all sectors that can boost the economy thanks to the creation of high-quality jobs and generation of economic growth	Big Data Value Association

SMEs	The backbone of the European economy (representing 99% of all EU businesses), providing a potential source for jobs and economic growth. Fast-growing businesses offering their products and services to develop Big Data driven innovation.	Digital SME Alliance; SMEunited; Digital Magics; DataCentric; MarineTraffic; Terrasigna; Digital Partners; InData Labs; Neuropublic SA; Nuromedia; Semantic Web Company; Spacelabel; Treelogic; Ubiwhere; amongst others.
Citizen Scientists	Members of the general public or non-professional scientists, engaging in scientific work and increasing in the public's understanding of science, with incompatible ways of handling and reusing different data sets.	Citizen Science COST Action; European Network Science Centres & Museums; Doing It Together Science; Citizen Science Centre Zurich, European Citizen Science Association; Citizen Cyberlab.

Value proposition	
Researchers	<p>Access to a European Network of FAIR trusted digital repositories through clustering and synchronisation activities.</p> <p>Training activities with research communities (e.g. working groups within EOSC-hub, GO-FAIR's GO-TRAIN and within ESFRI Clusters).</p> <p>Access to FAIRsFAIR offer with demonstrated sustainable platforms for making data FAIR and accessing FAIR data to use in research.</p> <p>A suite of tools, resources and measures facilitating FAIR implementation (data science schools for researchers, trainers and mentors, model courses in FAIR competences and reports).</p>
Industry (SMEs and Large Enterprises)	<p>Increase incomes thanks to the usage of data that follow FAIR principles.</p> <p>Hire new skilful professionals on data management and reduce the gap between total demand and supply of data workers.</p>
Citizen Scientists	<p>Training activities with research communities (e.g. working groups within EOSC-hub, GO-FAIR's GO-TRAIN and within ESFRI Clusters).</p> <p>Access to FAIRsFAIR offer with demonstrated sustainable access points.</p>

3.2. Implementers & Facilitators (secondary audience)

Universities and Research Performing Organisations, Specialised Service Providers, Policy Making Organisations, Research Funding Organisations & National Agencies, and Standard Development Organisations. The planned main activities are to encompass individual proposals to collaborate, one-on-one communication, requirements gathering via associations, and specific and tailored events and training sessions, and social media presence.

Stakeholder	Description	Sample
Universities & Research Performing Organisations	Any entity, irrespective of its legal status (organised under public or private law) or way of financing, whose primary goal is to conduct fundamental research, industrial research or experimental development and to disseminate their results by way of teaching, publication or technology transfer.	European University Association; Association of Research Organisations; European Association of Research and Technology Organisations; Young European Research Universities; All European Academies; SPARC Europe; and all European Universities dealing with research data
Research Funding Organisations & National Agencies	National research funders, charitable organisations and foundations, and other funders of research activity.	Science Europe
Specialised Service Providers	Service provider that enables data access on demand to users regardless of their geographic location, with information stored in the cloud and is accessible by a wide range of systems and devices	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives; Digital Repository of Ireland;
Policy Making Organisations	Governments, international entities, research funders, institutions, publishers, scientific associations and others defining data policy.	RDA FAIR DATA Maturity Model WGs; EC Expert Group on Turning FAIR Data into Reality; Committee on Data of the International Council for Science;
Standard Development Organisations	Formal organisations and consortia coordinating data standards and governing procedures relevant to FAIR, (e.g. repository certification, curriculum accreditation).	Digital Curation Centre

Value proposition

FAIRSFair will provide to all stakeholders in this category (Implementers & Facilitators) practice guidance on implementing the Rules of Participation (RoP) in the European Open Science Cloud, set as part of the governance framework to help participants offer and manage services and resources to the EOSC. The FAIR principles are at the core of the EOSC RoP.

<p>Universities & Research Performing Organisations</p>	<p>Access to an open, transparent and inclusive platform for consultation. Become a member in the network of trusted digital repositories and registry for FAIR compliant repositories. Share resources on FAIR skills via FAIR Competence Centre and knowledge base, contribute to and apply a tested Curriculum Framework for higher education New tools enabling identification of certified trustworthy repositories. A suite of tools, resources and measures facilitating FAIR implementation (data science schools for researchers, trainers and mentors, model courses in FAIR competences and reports). Capacity building on how to achieve appropriate certification and perform consistent peer reviews for certification. Compliant repositories, capability maturity model, consistent skills provision, consistent and usable vocabularies and metadata, to produce and re-use FAIR data more easily, efficiently and consistently. Certify data FAIRness through the certification badge for Core Trust Seal certified repositories, as well as a badging for assessment of FAIRness of individual datasets in trusted repositories.</p>
<p>Research Funding Organisations & National Agencies</p>	<p>Increase sustainable funding levels for FAIR implementation through new guidelines to include FAIR requirements on future funding programmes. Become aligned with certification schemes and sustainable business models to increase viability of research data management</p>
<p>Specialised Service Providers</p>	<p>Novel multiple business models and new income streams</p>
<p>Policy Making Organisations</p>	<p>Get updates about how to achieve the best possible usage of digital data to benefit the economy and society and support the nascent EOSC</p>
<p>Standard Development Organisations</p>	<p>Receive inputs on potential new standards towards the best possible usage of the potential of digital data to benefit the economy and society.</p>

3.3. Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures (other stakeholders)

End-Users and Implementers engaged with a mix of the activities described above.

Stakeholder	Description	Sample
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<p>Research Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures</p>	<p>Facilities, resources and related services that are used by the scientific community to conduct top-level research in their respective fields and covers major scientific equipment or sets of instruments.</p>	<p>E-Infrastructure Reflection Group; ENVRI-FAIR; EOSC-Life; ESCAPE, PANOSC; SSHOC; <i>CSC-IT Center for Science</i>;</p>
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Value proposition	
<p>Research Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures</p>	<p>Access to an open, transparent and inclusive platform for consultation. Become a member in the network of trusted digital repositories and registry for FAIR compliant repositories. Share resources on FAIR skills via FAIR Competence Centre and knowledge base, contribute to and apply a tested Curriculum Framework for higher education New tools enabling identification of certified trustworthy repositories. A suite of tools, resources and measures facilitating FAIR implementation (data science schools for researchers, trainers and mentors, model courses in FAIR competences and reports). Compliant repositories, capability maturity model, consistent skills provision, consistent and usable vocabularies and metadata, to produce and re-use FAIR data more easily, efficiently and consistently. Certify the level of trustworthiness of your data repository, as well as FAIRness evaluations at the dataset level. Simplify certification procedures and demonstrate how to certify the quality of a repository and acknowledged concept for assessing data usability/fitness for the use of individual datasets. Capacity building on how to achieve appropriate certification and perform consistent peer reviews for certification.</p>

3.4. Stakeholders Communication channels

Engagement will be measured by the number of stakeholders engaged and the dissemination activities that will be put in place, such as presence at physical or virtual events, social media messages, pieces of news published, communication material produced, amongst others. The central scope of the engagement directly translates into establishing a continuous dialogue with all the stakeholders selected. The following table indicates the main communication channels that will be used to engage with FAIRsFAIR different stakeholders.

Table 3 Communication Channels vs. Stakeholders FAIRsFAIR

FAIRsFAIR Communication Channels					
Channels	Researchers	Large Enterprises	SMEs	Citizen Scientists	Universities & Research Performing Organisations
Website	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications
Events	Invitation to key events: EOSC Workshop at Open Science Fair; EOSC event at RDA Finland; EOSC-hub week	Invitation to key events: EOSC Symposium	Invitation to key events: EOSC-hub week	Invitation to key events: EOSC-hub week	EOSC Workshop at Open Science Fair; EOSC event at RDA Finland
Webinars	1 webinar providing FAIR skills & insights			1 webinar providing FAIR skills & insights	1·1 Webinar: FAIR data practice analysis
Communication Materials	3 general flyers 3 Whitepapers for EOSC governance	3 general flyers	3 general flyers	3 general flyers	3 general flyers 3 Whitepapers for EOSC governance
Video interviews	1 video interview with stakeholder representative	1 video interview with stakeholder representative	1 video interview with stakeholder representative		1 video interview with stakeholder representative

Press Releases/ Articles	6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)	1 PR by end of the project targeting Industry		6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)	6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)
Newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters
Surveys/ Open Consultations	·Open call for support and guidance on FAIR Certification				Open call for support and guidance on FAIR Certification
Database	At least 15% contacts in database	1 % contacts in database	At least 10% contacts in database	At least 5% contacts in database	At least 15% contacts in database

FAIRsFAIR Communication Channels

Channels	Research Funding Organisations & National Agencies	Specialised Service Providers	Policy Making Organisations	Standard Development Organisations	Research Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
Website	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications	Timely updates with content-rich publications
Events	EOSC Workshop at Open Science Fair; EOSC event at RDA Finland; EOSC Symposium	EOSC-hub week	EOSC Symposium	EOSC-hub week	EOSC Workshop at Open Science Fair; EOSC event at RDA Finland; EOSC Symposium

Webinars	1 webinar providing FAIR skills & insights	1 webinar providing FAIR skills & insights	1 webinar providing FAIR skills & insights	1 webinar providing FAIR skills & insights	1 Webinar: FAIR data practice analysis
Communication Materials	3 general flyers 3 Whitepapers for EOSC governance	3 general flyers 3 Whitepapers for EOSC governance	3 general flyers 3 Whitepapers for EOSC governance relevant	3 general flyers 3 Whitepapers for EOSC governance	3 general flyers 3 Whitepapers for EOSC governance
Video interviews	1 video interview with stakeholder representative	1 video interview with stakeholder representative	1 video interview with stakeholder representative	1 video interview with stakeholder representative	1 video interview with stakeholder representative
Press Releases/ Articles	6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)	6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)	6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)	6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)	6 PR by end of the project (2 per year)
Newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters	Quarterly newsletters
Surveys/ Open Consultation	Open call for support and guidance on FAIR Certification; continuous landscape analysis				Open call for support and guidance on FAIR Certification; continuous landscape analysis
Database	At least 15% contacts in database	At least 10% contacts in database	At least 5% contacts in database	At least 7% contacts in database	At least 15% contacts in database

The communication strategy will promote FAIRSFair results to these stakeholders' communities, using the communication tools described in the following chapters.

4. FAIRSFAR results and assets for dissemination & communication

FAIRSFAR assets are its strengths and “selling” points and some of the key ones are summarised in the following sections. These points will be the focus of the FAIRSFAR communication, marketing and engagement strategy.

Figure 2 FAIRSFAR main outputs

4.1. FAIRSFAR Competence Framework

As part of WP7 (task 7.3), FAIRSFAR will develop by month 24 of the project (the first draft by month 20) a FAIR data competence framework complementary to or as an extension to existing and adopted data science and other competence frameworks (e.g. the ESCO-compliant EDISON Data Science FAIR Framework as well as the first is a skills and capability framework (FAIR4S) developed in the context of the EOSCpilot project - <https://eoscipilot.eu/content/d75-strategy-sustainable-development-skills-and-capabilities>). The activities will focus on data science but also address other disciplines, where identified as relevant, to enhance the impact and sustainability of the project in fostering a FAIR data culture throughout different scientific disciplines, research communities and professions

The FAIR data competence framework will include

- 1) FAIR data competences which can be acquired through higher education, e.g. in data science programmes in other data-intensive and data driven disciplines (all three cycles),
- 2) FAIR data competencies for graduates continuing to work as professionals in FAIR data management (e.g. data stewards, research infrastructure managers).

The expected competence framework will be targeted at institutions offering FAIR and data-related courses or aiming to do so. This will enable higher education institutions to address FAIR and related competences already during study experiences, e.g. at Bachelor, Master or PhD level, as opposed to professional trainings. By these means, FAIRSF AIR aims to support the supply of respective FAIR competences in Europe.

Specific promotion activities include:

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Webpage dedicated to the Competence Framework	1 web page on FAIRSF AIR website, launched at M20
Social media campaigns	Continuous Social media campaign, targeting in particular Universities and University Associations
Press release for the launch of the Competence Framework	1 Press release at the launch of the Competence Framework
Featured topic in FAIRSF AIR Newsletters	At least 3 news items featured in FAIRSF AIR newsletters related to the Competence Framework
Webinar	1 webinar to present the Competence Framework from M24 on

4.2. FAIRSF AIR Competence Centre and Training

As part of WP6 and WP7 FAIRSF AIR will ‘translate’ the competence framework into material usable by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This means the development of FAIR model courses and curricula for different disciplines and professional profiles (e.g. data scientists, data stewards and researchers in other disciplines) benefiting from FAIR data competences. This will include the definition of skills and competences according to European Qualification Framework (EQF) levels and by developing Intended Learning Outcomes and recommendations for learning assessment methods for first, second and third cycle learners in data science and other disciplines. A first draft of the **training handbook** is expected by month 28 with final delivery by month 34.

Universities will be acquainted with the framework and supporting training documents through three university workshops held in the second half of the project, and at the latest by month 32. This will ensure the diffusion of FAIR data competences throughout different scientific communities by specifically targeting university training programmes for early-stage researchers and future graduates in the first and second cycle of higher education.

Specific promotion activities include:

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Website visibility	Continuous development of training material for distribution through FAIRSF AIR website

Training handbook online	1 webpage with the training handbook available from M 28
Social media campaigns	Continuous Social media campaign, targeting in particular Universities and University Associations
Featured topic in FAIRsFAIR Newsletters	At least 3 news items featured in FAIRsFAIR newsletters related to the Competence Centre and training activities

4.3. FAIRsFAIR Tools, Resources and Services

FAIRsFAIR will develop and extend tools **for the assessment of FAIR datasets, a repository-finder tool and a service with which to access information about FAIR data, training, and services.** The latter will be a virtual competence centre which is thought to become a focal point of reference concerning FAIR data for all communities, providing a place to go for advice, training and services. The stakeholders for these tools and the service will be a broad, ranging from researchers, to infrastructure providers, to data managers and stewards.

Specific promotion activities include:

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Tools online pages	Different webpages for each of the tools and services, as part of the
Social media campaigns	Continuous Social media campaign, targeting in particular Universities and University Associations
Featured topic in FAIRsFAIR Newsletters	At least 3 news items featured in FAIRsFAIR newsletters related to the Competence Framework
Branding	Specific branding (icons) designed for each tool
FAIRsFAIR Services flyer	1 Flyer presenting all FAIRsFAIR services

FAIRsFAIR Certification

Trustworthy Data Repositories (TDRs) capable of curating FAIR data for researchers are a critical requirement for a European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The main objective of WP4 is to develop a sustainable certification approach for trusted data repositories holding FAIR digital research data in the EOSC. With this, FAIRsFAIR will play a key role in the development of global standards for FAIR certification of repositories and the data within them contributing to those policies and practices that will turn the EOSC programme into a functioning infrastructure.

In line with the “Turning FAIR into Reality” report from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data² FAIRsFAIR will augment existing certification mechanisms for digital data repositories, such as CoreTrustSeal. These established procedures and standards of the CoreTrustSeal requirements emerged from research data community work to identify key practices for data repositories which support long term access to reusable data.

² <https://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

An iterative approach will be taken to consider where FAIR object maturity can be aligned with the existing CoreTrustSeal requirements, and where additional requirements might be desirable. These Extended Requirements, supported by clear evaluated procedures, will provide the input for the iterative testing and revision of repository certification mechanisms for TDRs in the EOSC. Initial version of repository certification mechanism to be released in June 2020.

It is expected that the outcome of this approach is directly relevant to the CoreTrustSeal Requirements. Reference to FAIR and FAIR language being more incorporated in the CoreTrustSeal requirements will help researchers and data repositories to maintain their data FAIR in the long-term.

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Webpage dedicated to the FAIRSF AIR Certification	1 web page on FAIRSF AIR website
Social media campaigns	Continuous Social media campaign targeting the CoreTrustSeal community
Featured topic in FAIRSF AIR Newsletters	At least 1 news items featured in FAIRSF AIR newsletters related to the FAIRSF AIR Certification

5. Communication and Dissemination Plan

To support its objectives and generate the desiderated impact, FAIRSF AIR implements a 36-month communication strategy aimed at supporting the dissemination and stakeholder engagement targets of the project, coordinated under WP5 – “Engagement, Communication and Uptake”.

All the FAIRSF AIR partners contribute to community development and stakeholder engagement continuously throughout the project, as part of the project’s communication plan. They act as multipliers actors, engaging with specific communities of stakeholders.

Indeed, developing an effective communication scheme is the key to paving the way to dissemination and exploitation of results, to which all partners have committed according to availability dates and beyond the project lifecycle.

FAIRSF AIR benefits from asset coordination among the WPs, inside the consortium and collaboration with established organisations that can support the engagement of communities. The various stakeholder groups defined in this document will be addressed by engagement activities, aimed to enable the development and concrete realisation of an overall knowledge infrastructure on academic quality data management, procedures, standards, metrics and related matters based on the FAIR data principles.

5.1. The FAIRSF AIR Community

FAIRSF AIR works with a broad range of communities that will bring together their best practice from a range of domains – Universities and Researchers, Large Enterprises, SMEs, Services Providers, Policy Makers, National and International Infrastructures.

The project will support the communities in their activities aimed at FAIRs data uptake and compliance, promoting the harmonisation and coordination of efforts across communities, identifying opportunities for synergies and connections.

Moreover, in order to focus on the project’s goals, FAIRsFAIR develops and maps the Landscape Analysis and the integration of FAIR data principles among different communities. The HLAC and the EGFC will ensure coverage of all major groups with a balanced representation of viewpoints, priorities and needs.

The whole FAIRsFAIR community is already expanding, thanks to social media activity, event participation and partners’ multiplying efforts.

Our **Twitter** account is the main entrance point and content provider (together with the website) for our community; it already has 646 followers at the time of writing.

LinkedIn has 33 connections and the **YouTube** channel has shared at the moment 5 video-interviews made during the kick-off meeting, explaining the project, the objectives and the important connections with the FAIRsFAIR community.

A newsletter field has been built and implemented on the website, to disseminate the information and updates about the projects and the community itself, and a contact form will allow the project to reach a refined target of users and build a valued network database.

KPI	By M12	By M24	By M36
Overall size of the engaged community (Social media, Newsletter & Website registrations)	1000	2000	4000

5.2. FAIRsFAIR Web Platform

The FAIRsFAIR web platform fairsfair.eu is the unique access point and reference for the FAIRsFAIR project and it will gather and showcase the project’s main outputs and objectives, dedicating a part to the partners, news and events (organised by or related to FAIRsFAIR).

A preliminary version of the website was already up in M1 at project kick-off (March 2019).

Figure 2 - Website Landing Page

The first version of the FAIRsFAIR website was launched immediately after the Kickoff meeting (14 March 2019), providing information about the project and the communication activity. In M4 (June 2019) the newsletter subscription is available on the website. Users can register an account to receive the newsletter.

The FAIRsFAIR website is planned and structured to ensure visibility for all the FAIRsFAIR assets, namely the tools and services of the project, spread awareness of FAIR, also giving easy access to the main sections related to future actions and achieved goals. FAIRsFAIR website site map is presented below:

About

- The Project:
- The Partners
- Advisory committee (HLAC page)
- Reports and publications
- Synchronization Force
- FAIRsFAIR & EOSC Secretariat
- Collaborations

FAIR Champions

- EGFC
- EGFC Open call

FAIR Competence & Support *(in the future this could also include pages related to training and competence centres)*

- Open Call for data repositories
- Training handbook
- Competence centre materials

FAIR Certification (a page including the reports by WP4)

Competence Framework

Events

- FAIRsFAIR events
- Other events

Media

- News
- Videos
- Social Media sentiment
- Communication Kit

Contact

The FAIRsFAIR website will have different iterations during the project's lifetime aligned with the forthcoming results and Milestones.

5.3. Content Driven approach

The communication, marketing and engagement plan will concentrate its efforts around copywriting and producing engaging, stimulating and impactful content. Our editorial planning will include the **regular publication of articles covering project updates, updated events calendars with their outputs, news pieces about FAIRsFAIR Landscape analysis and open calls, and information in the research and FAIR data field.**

To build and relate the FAIRsFAIR roadmap, additional inputs will be required from partners, linked third organisations, and from the FAIRsFAIR community. In this content-driven approach also all the events and communities' messages will be disseminated.

The FAIRsFAIR group of 22 partners gathers together research and university organisations and communities, with the aim to contribute to the FAIR culture across EU society, implement a common scheme to ensure compliance with FAIR data principles and practices through the EOSC, support the communities in their activities and increase the use of FAIR data for the stakeholders in the research field. **Partners' highlights** will also be used to be included in communication activities, posted on the website and used for social media content and articles.

KPI	By M12
Content production	Min. 20 new content items/month; 20,000 monthly sessions, 10,000 users, 80,000 page views)

5.4. FAIRsFAIR Visual identity and branding

The communication and marketing activities will use a consistent visual identity to underline the consistent message around FAIR concept:

- Logos and payoffs for all the documents and online & offline activities (website, social media, video production, etc)
- Templates for external communication and presentations
- Complementary look and feel on website and social media channels
- Collaterals and publications (flyers and posters) with a common branding

Figure 3 - FAIRsFAIR Visual Identity

5.5. Step-by-step promotion of events through FAIRsFAIR outreach channels

One of the central points for FAIRsFAIR communication and marketing is the promotion of events and workshops, their coverage and follow up, through website and social media channels

Figure 4 - Sample Tweets for FAIRsFAIR event

5.6. Examples of messaging and value proposition

FAIRsFAIR Social Activities are focused on objective-oriented and content-rich posts that explain the value, the concept and the aim of the project. Hashtags and images follow the message and videos with all the actors and partners will be proposed to the community, in order to engage and support the FAIR DATA culture.

Figure 5 - Example of messages with value proposition

5.7. Visibility at Events

All the FAIRsFAIR related events, workshops and webinars are already and will be communicated in a dedicated section on the website and will be covered pre, during and after the event.

Before the event, FAIRsFAIR will promote “save the date” posts and twitter cards, write a related news post and refer to all linked third-parties and partners.

Collaterals will help to build the identity and harmonise the Communication, Marketing and Engagement Plan.

Examples of FAIRsFAIR rollup banner, pins and stickers with a common identity are provided below

Figure 6 - Collaterals at the kick-off meeting

5.8. KPI-driven approach

Evaluation of the Communication and Marketing activities will be based on several points. Measurable impacts (KPIs) are tracked on a monthly basis through a “Flash Report” monitoring the visibility, engagement, and dissemination potential of online activities in automated software which extracts, analyses, and visualises the selected figures.

An online Dashboard will be set up to measure the online presence and the community engagement.

Also, publication of articles, reports from the related organisations, magazines and white papers from researchers’ communities will be monitored.

6. Communication Toolkit

The toolbox aims to ensure the timely delivery of high-quality materials and tools supporting stakeholder engagement with messages tailored to various levels of knowledge. The communication toolkit aims to align and facilitate the engagement and communication for FAIRSF AIR project partners and stakeholders. The toolbox is KPI-based for communications and stakeholder engagement, as described in the following table for M4-M36.

Content production

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Articles specifically written for CORDIS RESEARCH EU, CORDIS Results Packs, and Digital Single Market blogs for timely information about FAIRSF AIR results	2 CORDIS Articles per year 2 DSM newsletter publications per year focusing on FAIRSF AIR results

Press releases / articles on key milestones of FAIRsFAIR targeting stakeholders (policy, citizen, industry)	M2 press releases per year / up to 6
Scientific paper on FAIRsFAIR outcomes	At least 3 papers/peer reviewed articles acknowledging FAIRsFAIR per year
FAIRsFAIR value proposition pages	6 pages online (1 per WP)
FAIRsFAIR partners value propositions	Quotes by partners in the partners pages; social media posts
Online surveys	12 surveys (mini and more detailed) with published results.
Continuous publication of content on the website	Min. 20 new content items/month; 20,000 monthly sessions, 10,000 users, 80,000 page views

Flyers, Factsheets, infographics, posters, roll-ups

Activity	KPIs for the overall project
Flyer for FAIRsFAIR Open Calls & Landscape Analysis promotion	3 flyers focusing on the Landscape Analysis, the Open calls surveys and FAIRsFAIR main assets
Infographic	1 infographics about FAIRsFAIR offering
Roll-up	1 roll-up
1-pager for FAIRsFAIR Tools and Services	
1 Training Handbook readable version (online & printable)	
Stickers, pins and other giveaways	On a case by case

Videos

Activity	KPI for the overall project
1 overall video about FAIRSF AIR	1 video
Video interviews with FAIRSF AIR stakeholders	At least 10 in total
Video interviews with FAIRSF AIR partners	At least 10 in total out of 22 partners

Newsletters and email marketing

The FAIRSF AIR project will be disseminating its results through quarterly newsletters. Direct email marketing will also be used for press-releases via the contacts established with the different stakeholders communication teams.

Activity	KPI
FAIRSF AIR newsletters	4/year, 12 in total
Direct email marketing to stakeholders communities	upon request

Social Media Strategy

The Social Media strategy is designed in tiers, each of them aligned with the specific promotional and communication campaigns targeting:

1. Landscape analysis and open calls
2. FAIRSF AIR assets and tools
3. FAIRSF AIR training & competence framework
4. FAIRSF AIR Events
5. FAIRSF AIR in general

Activity	KPI
Overall Social media connections	Min. 10 tweets/retweets week Min. 5 posts/month on other social media channels, monitored in terms of visibility, brand and reputation building
Webinars	6 webinars organised with 40 members attending on average
YouTube	250 monthly views and 5 acquired subscriptions to the YouTube channel. Impact measures based on number of views